

Speculation on the Notion of Probability in 2-Slit Interference Part 2

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A two slit apparatus consists of two slits separated by solid material. The validation of this description comes from a special measurement. In particular, one must use a photon with a wavelength much smaller than the width of the slits and also of their separation. Only under those circumstances does the measurement interaction describe the apparatus in the manner above. In particular, in that case, motion through one slit or the other means interaction with one slit or the other not both. In addition, given that there are two openings, any photon, regardless of its wavelength $hbar/p$, must pass through one slit or the other. If the wavelength, however, is of the order of the slit widths and separation, then an interaction occurs with both, as we argued in Part I, and an entangled state is created. Thus, unlike classical physics, there is the possibility of an entangled state. In fact, we argue that this is the more natural (or more descriptive, less restrictive state) and the so-called classical state associated with one slit, more restrictive.

This particular entangled state is one of many possible as one might have a single slit (with width about $hbar/p$) or 3-slits etc. In addition, one may have a measuring device which captures less information about the quantum free particle, which we call a restrictive measurement. As noted in Part I, one may place detectors behind each slit. Even though a photon or particle may be in an entangled state (interacting with both slits), it must pass through one slit or the other. Thus, its physical presence is by one slit or the other allowing a detector behind a particular slit to capture it and force it, so to speak, to only interact with that detector. This is a restrictive measurement which erases the information of the entangled state, i.e. of the interaction with both slits. It is as if the photon now originates from this detector and one no longer knows about the $\exp(ipx)$ feature of the quantum free particle. If one were to place a second 2-slit apparatus behind the detector, however, a new entangled state would be created, again manifesting the more general $\exp(ipx)$ properties of the quantum free particle.

In Part I, we argued briefly that this was similar to the case of measuring spin $\frac{1}{2}$ projections. Again, a restrictive measurement occurs if one measures the z-projection of spin as an entangled state is the more general one. If one performs a second measurement, namely an x-projection, then this is restrictive in the x direction, but it undoes the restriction imposed by the first measurement in the z direction. In other words, the z direction reverts to the more general state of an entangled spin up or down, just as the second 2-slit apparatus undoes the restricted measurement of the detector placed behind one slit. This suggests a rotational nature to spin, we argue. Furthermore, in both cases we see that an entangled state is the more revealing -less restrictive state of the quantum object.

Classical Physics and the notion of an Entangled State

Measurements are performed to determine properties of a particle or photon. For example, a target may be used to determine the magnitude and direction of momentum. Even in classical physics, however, measurements do not necessarily reveal all possible properties of a particle. For example, a record on a turntable turns in one direction due to a certain torque, but one cannot conclude that it could not turn in the opposite direction. The difference with quantum

mechanics, however, is that classical physics considers distinct states (like heads or tails for a coin), but not entangled states. In quantum mechanics, one may have “natural” entangled states which seem strange classically only because of certain classical constraints that one imposes on a situation for which they do not apply.

For example, a two-slit apparatus is described by two slits with the same width and a separation. This description, however, follows from a measurement using a photon with a wavelength much smaller than width or separation of the slits. It does not follow from a measurement using a wavelength of the order of the slit width/separation. This means that the description of the slit apparatus is measurement dependent. In the case of $\hbar/p \ll$ slit width/separation, a photon not only passes through one slit or the other (always the case regardless of wavelength), but only interacts with one slit or the other. This second feature related to interaction, however, only applies to $\hbar/p \ll$ slit width/separation and cannot be generalized to all wavelengths which seems to be done if one adopts a classical viewpoint.

A quantum free particle is associated with a complex probability $\exp(ipx)$ which allows it to interact with both slits if the slit width/separation is about \hbar/p . This leads to an entangled state, which is not classical, describes the properties of the quantum free particle fairly well. The 2-slit apparatus is not unique in trying to describe $\exp(ipx)$. One could use a 3-slit, 4-slit etc apparatus or even a single slit apparatus as long as widths/separations are of the order of \hbar/p . Thus, as in Part I, we argue that the entangled state is a “natural” state corresponding to the properties of $\exp(ipx)$ and not some kind of statistical mixture as in the case of the math description of a tossed coin. A tossed coin is not in an entangled state of heads up or down, rather there is a probability to have one or the other.

Restrictive Measurements

A quantum free particle is associated with $\exp(ipx)$, but as noted in Part I, one requires a special type of measurement, one linked to a wavelength, to discern this. Not all measurements do so. As a result, one may create an entangled state by having a photon interact with a 2-slit apparatus with widths/spacing of the order of \hbar/p . Physically, however, the photon passes through one slit or the other, but unlike the case of $\hbar/p \ll$ slit width/separation one cannot say that the interaction is only with one slit or the other. One may, however, introduce a restrictive measurement so that the position of the photon/particle restricts its interaction. This is done by placing detectors just behind each slit. If a photon/particle passes through slit 1, then the detector there forces or restricts it to only interact with itself and not the detector behind the second slit. It is then as if the photon is created at this detector. The photon/particle, however, still retains its $\exp(ipx)$ nature which may then interact with a second 2-slit apparatus which erases the restrictive constraint of the detector measurement. In other words, the second 2-slit apparatus reveals more of the nature of $\exp(ipx)$ than the single detector behind a slit.

Spin $\frac{1}{2}$ Projections

In Part I, we argued that the above ideas related to 2-slit interference/diffraction are linked to spin $\frac{1}{2}$ projection measurements. This seems to imply that an entangled state for projections seems to more generally capture the physical properties of a spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particle. In such a case,

measuring the z projection is a restrictive measurement, like the single detectors behind each slit. It changes the more general entangled state into a restrictive single projection state which does not fully describe the nature of the spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particle. Classically, however, it seems that one would consider a single projection as a natural state and an entangled one as some kind of probabilistic situation. Here we argue that the reverse is true. The entangled state is the natural one and the restricted one represents partial information and its appearance is linked to probability.

One may perform a second restrictive measurement, this time along the x-axis. In this case, one obtains a restricted single projection value state along the x axis, but undoes the restriction along the z-axis, just as a second 2-slit apparatus undoes the restrictive measurement and ensuing state of a single detector behind a slit. The fact that a restrictive measurement in the x direction undoes a restriction in the z direction seems to suggest a rotational property associated with spin. Furthermore, it shows that an entangled state is the more revealing or natural state of a spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particle.

Thus, an unusual feature of quantum mechanics (as compared with classical mechanics) seems to be the notion of entangled states. Classically, one expects interaction with only one slit or only one spin projection. The entangled state, however, seems to be a natural state and should not be depicted as a probability combination of two single states as in the case of a coin toss. This is why a superposition occurs at the level of the wavefunction W , and not at the classical level of W^*W , it seems.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that quantum objects seem to have properties linked to entangled states, unlike classical mechanics. For example, classically a particle not only passes through one slit or the other in a 2-slit apparatus, but only interacts with the walls of one slit or the other. Quantum mechanically, this only holds if $\hbar/p \ll \text{slit width/separation}$. In other words, it is physically incorrect to suggest that interaction with only one slit occurs if \hbar/p is of the order of the slit width/separation. This leads to a new kind of state, an entangled one, which is completely consistent with the $\exp(ipx)$ properties of the quantum free particle, but which seems strange from a classical viewpoint. It is possible, however, to introduce restrictive measurements into quantum mechanics which force a quantum particle into a state which only reveals part of its properties. From a classical point of view, it seems that such a state is natural, but we argue here that it is restrictive and that the entangled state is more natural, and the latter restrictive. The kind of restriction imposed is then associated with a probability. In particular, a quantum particle/photon may form an entangled state at a 2-slit apparatus. The particle, however, can only pass through one slit or the other, and so one may place a detector behind each. In this way, if the photon/particle passes through slit 1, the detector there forces or restricts it into a state showing no entanglement. One may, however, undo this restrictive state by having the photon/particle pass through a second 2-slit apparatus (\hbar/p of the order of the slit widths/separation) because the $\exp(ipx)$ property of the quantum particle is not destroyed. It is only hidden by the detector behind slit 1. Note: There is equal probability for the particle to pass through one slit or the other, but differently weighted entangled states are possible.

We also argue that similar arguments apply to the restrictive measurement of spin projection for a spin $\frac{1}{2}$ particle. Classically, a given projection might seem like the more natural or physical state, but we argue that actually it is the entangled state which is the more natural one. A projection measurement along the z axis restricts the full description of quantum spin. A second restrictive measurement along the x axis (after the one along the z axis), however, undoes the restriction in the z direction. Now the restriction is along the x axis. This suggests a rotational feature of spin as a restriction along one axis undoes it along another.